

Effectiveness of Software Quality Assurance in Offshore Development Enterprises in Sri Lanka

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Abstract : The aim of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness of software quality assurance approaches of Sri Lankan offshore software development organizations, and to propose a framework which could be used across all offshore software development organizations. An empirical study was conducted using derived framework from popular software quality evaluation models. The research instrument employed was a questionnaire survey among thirty seven Sri Lankan registered offshore software development organizations. The findings demonstrate a positive view of Effectiveness of Software Quality Assurance - the stronger predictors of Stability, Installability, Correctness, Testability and Changeability. The present study's recommendations indicate a need for much emphasis on software quality assurance for the Sri Lankan offshore software development organizations.

Keywords : software quality assurance (SQA), offshore software development, quality assurance evaluation models, effectiveness of quality assurance

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